

Stability and structure of some metal complexes involving tri- and tetra-dentate Schiff bases

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Abstract : Equilibrium studies involved in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} -2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (pyal)(A)-L-glutamic acid (glu) and L-aspartic acid (asp)(B) systems at $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3) show the formation of the Schiff base complexes of stoichiometry $\text{M}(\text{AB})$, $\text{M}(\text{AB})\text{A}$ and $\text{M}(\text{AB})_2$. Both the stability constant and electronic spectral data indicate that in $\text{M}(\text{AB})$ and $\text{M}(\text{AB})\text{A}$ complexes, the Schiff base (AB) is tetradentate, while in $\text{M}(\text{AB})_2$ the Schiff base functions as tridentate. The electronic spectral measurements indicate that $\text{Co}(\text{AB})$ complex do have tetrahedral structure, while the $\text{Ni}(\text{AB})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{AB})$ complexes have square planar geometry. The $\text{M}(\text{AB})_2$ complexes in the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} systems were found to have octahedral structure. Mulliken charge density and atomic orbital population analysis for the Schiff base ligands have also been done.

Keywords : Metal complexes, Schiff base, 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde.

Coordination chemistry in metalloproteins is dominated by amino acids since amino acid side chains and backbone heteroatoms entail the majority of ligands available to coordinate to metal ions¹. Small molecule models of metal sites in metalloproteins are an integral part of bioinorganic chemistry, and the design of new ligands to model challenging structural and/or functional motifs plays an important role in the development of new model complexes². Enzymes like alcoholdehydrogenase accept 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde as substrate. The derivative of 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde viz. 2-pyridinealdoxime methiodide has been effectively used in the therapeutical treatment of organophosphorous poisoning. The pyridine nitrogen, which is a very good donor is present close to the -CHO group in 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde makes the Schiff bases formed by 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde powerful chelates. In continuation of our earlier studies on Schiff base complexes^{3-5,11}, the present paper reports the Schiff base complex equilibria involved in Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} -2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (pyal)(A)-L-glutamic acid (glu) and L-aspartic acid (asp) (B) systems at $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3).

Results and discussion

The Schiff bases are non-planar. The pyridine ring and imino nitrogens are in a plane and the carboxylato groups are in the axial position. From the Mulliken charge density analysis⁶, it has been found that Schiff bases can bind through pyridine nitrogen, imino nitrogen and two carboxylato oxygens (Table 1). Due to anion formation the

charges on the pyridine nitrogen and carboxylato oxygens are increased, but charge on the imino nitrogen decreases. This may be due to the electron withdrawing nature of the carboxylato group. The potential donor groups in the pyal-asp Schiff base are the pyridine nitrogen and imino nitrogen which bind through p_z and α and β carboxylato oxygens which bind through p_x and p_y orbitals. In the case of pyal-glu Schiff base, the pyridine nitrogen and imino nitrogen bind through p_x (Table 1) and the α and β carboxylato oxygens use p_z and p_x orbitals for coordination.

Table 1. Mulliken charge density and atomic orbital population analysis (AOP)

	pyl-asp			pyl-glu		
	Neu	Anion	AOP	Neu	Anion	AOP
py-N	-0.1375	-0.1561	p_z	-0.1414	-0.1526	p_y
Imino-N	-0.1679	-0.1031	p_z	-0.1616	-0.0991	p_x
α -O	-0.3074	-0.5544	p_x	-0.3031	-0.5329	p_z
O	-0.3171	-0.6059	p_y	-0.3174	-0.6136	p_x

Three types of ternary complexes of stoichiometry MAB , MA_2B and MA_2B_2 were detected in the systems under investigation. The stability constant and electronic spectral data are given in Tables 2 and 3.

Stability and structure of MAB complexes :

The $\log \beta_{\text{Co}(\text{AB})}$ values obtained in the Co^{II} -pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems are respectively 10.99 and 11.35. If the

ligands A and B were considered to bind Co^{II} independently forming mixed ligand complexes, then the respective statistically calculated values⁷ of $\log \beta_{\text{Co(AB)}}$ would be 6.38 and 7.12. The higher experimental values can be explained by considering the interligand interaction between pyal and glu/asp to form a Schiff base which form a stable Schiff base complex Co(AB) . The $\log \beta_{\text{Co(AB)}}$ values obtained in these systems are higher than that of 10.29 in the Co^{II} -pyal(A)-val(B) system³, where the Schiff base (AB) formed is tridentate. This indicates that Schiff base (AB) in Co^{II} -pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems binds Co^{II} through all the four possible donor atoms viz. pyridine and imino nitrogen and both carboxylato oxygen atoms.

Table 2. Stability constants in the M^{II} -pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) Schiff base complex systems

Systems	$\log \beta_{\text{MAB}}$	$\log \beta_{\text{MA}_2\text{B}}$	$\log \beta_{\text{MA}_2\text{B}_2}$	$\log K_{\text{MA}_2\text{B}}^{\text{MAB}}$
Co^{II} -pyal(A)-glu(B)	10.99	12.91	16.72	1.92
Co^{II} -pyal(A)-asp(B)	11.35	13.29	16.93	1.88
Ni^{II} -pyal(A)-glu(B)	12.46	14.58	19.25	2.06
Ni^{II} -pyal(A)-asp(B)	13.10	15.16	19.68	2.06
Cu^{II} -pyal(A)-glu(B)	18.00	-	-	-
Cu^{II} -pyal(A)-asp(B)	18.42	-	-	-
Zn^{II} -pyal(A)-glu(B)	11.16	12.94	17.41	1.78
Zn^{II} -pyal(A)-asp(B)	11.58	13.38	17.64	1.80

The $\log \beta_{\text{M(AB)}}$ values in the Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} -pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems are respectively 12.46 and 13.10; 18.0 and 18.42 and 11.16 and 11.58 (Table 2). The $\log \beta_{\text{MAB}}$ values theoretically calculated⁷ for the mixed ligand complexes where A and B bind the metal independently in the MAB species in Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} -pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems are respectively 7.65 and 8.57; 10.45 and 10.53 and 6.64 and 6.84. By putting forward the arguments under Co^{II} -pyal(A)-glu(B) system it can be concluded that in M(AB) species in all the systems in the present study, the Schiff base ligand is tetradentate. M(AB) complexes of M^{II} -pyal(A)-glu(B) systems will have two five and one seven membered rings, whereas those in the M^{II} -pyal(A)-asp(B) systems will have two five and one six membered rings, which should be more stable (Table 2).

Table 3. Electronic spectral data of metal Schiff base complex systems

Systems	Complex species	λ_{max} (nm)	Geometry
Co^{II} -pyal(A)-asp(B)	CoAB	640	Tetrahedral
	Co(AB)_2	776, 475	Octahedral
Ni^{II} -pyal(A)-asp(B)	NiAB	495	Square planar
	Ni(AB)_2	898, 641, 367	Octahedral
Cu^{II} -pyal(A)-asp(B)	CuAB	643	Square planar

The species distribution diagrams in the Co^{II} -pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems indicate that Schiff base complexes Co(AB) is the predominant species in the pH range 7.0 to

8.0 reaching a maximum of 60% of the total metal ion. In the Ni^{II} -pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems, concentration of the Ni(AB) species is comparable to that of the binary species NiB and NiB_2 in the 1 : 1 system. However, in the 1 : 2 systems, the Ni(AB) complexes are predominant between pH 7.0 and 8.0. In the Cu^{II} -pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems, Cu(AB) is predominant in the pH range 5.5–7.0, reaching a maximum of 75%. In the Zn^{II} -pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems the Schiff base complex Zn(AB) was found to be more favoured between pH 7.0 and 8.0. In order to demonstrate this qualitative trends, the diagram obtained for Co^{II} -pyal-glu system is given in Fig. 1.

Table 4. Dissociation constants and stability constants for the parent binary complexes with M^{II} -pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems (Ref. 3 and 9)

Metal Co^{II}	Ligand	$\log \beta_{\text{HA}}$	$\log \beta_{\text{MA}}$	$\log \beta_{\text{MA}_2}$	$\log \beta_{\text{H}_2\text{B}}$	$\log \beta_{\text{H}_2\text{B}}$	$\log \beta_{\text{MB}}$	$\log \beta_{\text{MB}_2}$
Co^{II}	pyal	3.84	1.75	3.45	-	-	-	-
	glu	-	-	-	4.23	9.46	5.36	8.70
	asp	-	-	-	3.79	9.50	5.90	10.18
Ni^{II}	pyal	-	1.98	3.90	-	-	-	-
	glu	-	-	-	-	-	6.10	10.80
	asp	-	-	-	-	-	7.09	12.64
Cu^{II}	pyal	-	2.65	4.99	-	-	-	-
	glu	-	-	-	-	-	8.75	15.30
	asp	-	-	-	-	-	8.70	15.46
Zn^{II}	pyal	-	1.67	3.27	-	-	-	-
	glu	-	-	-	-	-	5.10	9.40
	asp	-	-	-	-	-	5.68	9.84

The electronic spectrum of Co(AB) complex in the Co^{II} -pyal(A)-asp(B) system, recorded at pH 7.47 in the 1 : 1 system shows an absorption band at 640 nm. This corresponds to the ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition⁸ arising due to the tetrahedral environment of ligand field around Co^{II} . Hence, Co(AB) complex can be assigned a tetrahedral structure. The

Fig. 1. Species distribution diagram for the Co^{II} -pyal(A)-glu(B) system (metal : A = 1 : 1) : (1) unbound Co^{II} , (2) CoA , (3) CoA_2 , (4) CoB , (5) CoB_2 , (6) CoAB , (7) CoA_2B , (8) CoA_2B_2 .

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Ni(AB) complex in the Ni^{II}-pyal(A)-asp(B) system, in its electronic spectrum recorded at pH 7.30 in the 1 : 2 system exhibits one broad absorption band at 495 nm. This corresponds to the $^3A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3B_{1g}$ transition in square planar configuration. The electronic absorption spectrum of Cu(AB) complex in the Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-asp(B) system, measured at pH 6.24 in the 1 : 1 system shows a broad absorption band at 643 nm. This peak corresponds to square planar geometry of Cu^{II}. The same type of geometries have also been reported¹¹ for the M(AB) complexes in the Co^{II}/Ni^{II}-pyal-glu systems.

Stability and structure of MA₂B complex :

The experimental log β values of CoA₂B complexes in the Co^{II}-pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems are 12.91 and 13.23, while the theoretically calculated values for simple mixed ligand complexes are 8.10 and 8.84. Similarly, the experimental log β values for the Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}-pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems are respectively 14.58 and 15.16 and 12.94 and 13.38, whereas the statistically calculated values for mixed ligand complexes are 9.60 and 10.52 and 8.27 and 8.49 respectively. The higher experimental values clearly show that MA₂B complexes are Schiff base complexes of the type M(AB)(A). The formation constant values of M(AB)A from MAB are comparable to those of MA₂ from MA. Hence, in the M(AB)A complexes the Schiff base (AB) can bind the metal ion in tetradentate mode and the second pyal is coordinated through its pyridine nitrogen alone. The M(AB)A type of complexes were found to be predominant above pH 7.0 (Fig. 1).

Stability and structure of MA₂B₂ complexes :

This type of complex species has been detected in the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}-pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems. The log β values obtained are 16.72 and 16.93 for Co^{II}, 19.25 and 19.68 for Ni^{II} and 17.41 and 17.64 for Zn^{II} systems (Table 2). These values are much higher than those of 12.45 and 13.93 for CoA₂B₂, 15.00 and 16.84 for NiA₂B₂ and 12.97 and 13.41 for ZnA₂B₂, theoretically calculated values for the mixed ligand complexes⁷ without interligand interaction. This distinctly shows that the MA₂B₂ complexes are bis(Schiff base) complexes of the type M(AB)₂. Here both the Schiff bases (AB) would coordinate in tridentate mode giving a coordination number of six to the metal ion. In the M^{II}-pyal(A)-glu and asp(B) systems they can bind the metal ion through the pyridine and imino nitrogen and the α -carboxylato oxygen atom resulting in a structure with two

pairs of five membered rings. If the γ -carboxylato group is involved in coordination, then the complex would contain two five and two seven membered rings, which will be sterically unfavourable.

The M(AB)₂ complexes are found to be present in higher concentration at higher pH and particularly in the systems where M^{II} : pyal is kept at 1 : 2. The electronic spectrum of the Co(AB)₂ complex in the Co^{II}-pyal(A)-asp(B) system, recorded at pH 8.48 in the 1 : 2 system exhibits two peaks at 776 and 445 nm. The higher frequency peak is more intense. These absorptions correspond to the transitions of Co^{II} in octahedral geometry viz. $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$ (776 nm) and $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ (445 nm).

The Ni(AB)₂ species obtained in the Ni^{II}-pyal(A)-asp(B) system, in its electronic spectrum measured at pH 8.45 in the 1 : 2 system shows three absorption bands at 898, 641 and 367 nm, of which the peak at 367 nm is more intense. These absorptions correspond to the *d-d* transitions of Ni^{II} in the octahedral environment of the ligand field. Thus M(AB)₂ complexes in the Co^{II}, Ni^{II}-pyal-asp systems have octahedral geometry as similar to those in the Co^{II}, Ni^{II}-pyal-glu systems¹¹.

Experimental

The computational studies were carried out using the package MOPAC 6.0 using AM1Hameltonian⁶. glu and asp were purchased from Fluka. pyal was purchased from Lancaster. Metal nitrates were purchased from B.D.H. All other reagents and solvents were purchased from commercial sources and were analytical grade. The binary stability constants of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with pyal, glu and asp under the present experimental conditions were taken from the literature^{3,9} (Table 4). In the Schiff base complex systems, a batchwise titration procedure was used³⁻⁵. The pH data were analysed using a computer program¹⁰ designed for the evaluation of Schiff base complex equilibria. The electronic spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 3B UV-Vis spectrophotometer by adopting the procedure described earlier^{3-5,11}.

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